

Improvements in the CW Evaluation of Mode-Stirred Chambers

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Abstract: We present methods for improving the reliability of measurements made in a mode-stirred chamber. The combination of improved instrumentation and a larger paddle resulted in measurements that were significantly more reproducible (± 1 dB) than previous measurements. We also give a simple model that is capable of describing the characteristics of a mode-stirred chamber at any frequency using only two parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Mode-stirred chamber measurements suffer from the reputation of having large uncertainties. This reputation has been well deserved in the past, with typical uncertainties between ± 3 dB and ± 10 dB cited in the literature [1]. These large uncertainties are due primarily to poor measurement reproducibility, which accounts for most (between ± 2 dB and ± 8 dB) of the total uncertainty associated with the measurements.

Poor reproducibility can be traced to two principal sources: fluctuations as a result of placement of equipment and devices inside the chamber, referred to as fluctuations in spatial uniformity, and the reproducibility of the instrumentation and equipment (such as cables and adapters) used in the measurement. Recent measurements made by NIST have shown that the spatial uniformity can be improved by simple and inexpensive modifications to the chamber, and the reproducibility of the instrumentation and equipment can be improved by the selection of stable instrumentation and improved calibration techniques. The combination of these techniques can result in reproducibilities of approximately 1 dB.

BACKGROUND

A mode-stirred chamber is an electrically large, highly conductive enclosed cavity used to measure electromagnetic compatibility (both emissions and immunity) of electronic devices. A mechanical conductive stirrer or paddle is used to change the mode structure inside the chamber. A typical measurement setup for the evaluation of a mode-stirred chamber is shown in Fig. 1. A CW signal is transmitted into the chamber through an antenna. The power transmitted into the chamber is measured by a sensor on each sidearm of a directional coupler. The term sensor is used to refer to an

arbitrary RF measuring device, typically a power meter or spectrum analyzer. Some of the power that enters the chamber is coupled to another sensor through a second antenna.

The goal of this measurement is to predict the power that will be picked up by the receiving antenna as a function of the power transmitted into the chamber. In such a complex environment, this task is extremely difficult, if not impossible for any given position of the paddle. When the paddle is moved, however, the electromagnetic environment inside the chamber is randomized, and it becomes possible to predict the statistical characteristics of the received signal. In this paper, we are primarily interested in the average received power, although other electromagnetic properties can also be evaluated.

THEORY

The chamber gain G_C is the ratio of the received power P_R to the transmitted power P_T , measured at a specific paddle position. If P_T is held constant, then G_C will be proportional to P_R . In this paper we restrict our attention to the properties of G_C averaged over a large number of paddle positions. We will use the symbols $\langle \rangle$ to represent such an average, with

$$\langle G_C \rangle = \frac{\langle P_R \rangle}{P_T} \quad (1)$$

The average chamber gain is closely related to the chamber quality factor Q , which has been well documented. The

Figure 1. Typical mode-stirred chamber measurement setup.

quality factor is proportional to the average chamber gain and the cube of the CW excitation frequency

$$Q \propto \langle G_C \rangle f^3. \quad (2)$$

Hill et al. [2] show that the quality factor of a chamber can be described by four components, Q_1 , Q_2 , Q_3 , and Q_4 . Q_1 is the quality factor that would be observed if absorption by the chamber walls were the only loss mechanism present in the chamber. Similarly, Q_2 corresponds to absorption by a device in the chamber, Q_3 relates to leakage from the chamber through apertures, and Q_4 is the quality factor that would be observed in a perfectly conducting cavity, with all power absorbed by terminations connected to antennas. For an empty chamber (a chamber with no apertures and containing only antennas), only Q_1 and Q_4 are significant, and we can write the total Q for an empty chamber as

$$Q^{-1} = Q_1^{-1} + Q_4^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

As shown in [2], for a chamber made of a nonmagnetic material and at wavelengths significantly larger than the surface roughness of the material, Q_1 is proportional to $f^{1/2}$, and Q_4 is proportional to f^3 . By combining equations (2) and (3) and the frequency dependence of Q_1 and Q_4 , we can write $\langle G_C \rangle$ as

$$\langle G_C \rangle = \frac{1}{a + b \cdot f^{5/2}}. \quad (4)$$

Ideally, the value of a will be equal to the number of receiving antennas in the chamber (if N identical antennas are placed in a chamber, on average, each antenna will receive the same amount of power). Also, b should be calculable from the material properties of the cavity.

Figure 2. Chamber gain and estimated curve fit measured in NIST chamber. Data taken from NBS Tech. Note 1092.

Unfortunately, due to imperfections in instrumentation and material parameter estimates, a priori estimates of a and b are not always reliable. Instead, we can use nonlinear curve

fitting to obtain estimates of the parameters a and b . Figure 2 shows data measured in the NIST chamber and previously presented in NBS Tech. Note 1092 [1]. These data have been reprocessed to give a measure of G_C . The estimated curve fit is also presented.

MEASUREMENT REPRODUCIBILITY

The reproducibility of a measurement is a gauge of the variations between measurements after a significant change has been made in the system, such as repositioning antennas, recalibrating the system, or changing instrumentation. Recent measurements have shown that a large change in frequency also appears to qualify as a significant change, and as a result, the fluctuations in G_C about the estimated curve fit can be used to estimate the reproducibility of the measurement and the measurement system.

Figure 3. Residuals of chamber gain measured in NIST chamber. Based on data taken from NBS Tech. Note 1092.

Figure 3 shows a plot of G_C divided by the estimated curve fit. We will refer to the data in such plots as the residuals of the chamber gain. The residuals allow us to compare the reproducibility of measurements made in different chambers in a consistent manner. We will estimate the reproducibility of G_C as 2 times the standard deviation of the residuals, where the standard deviation is calculated as if the residuals at each frequency were a new measurement. This method of estimating the reproducibility yields results which are similar to “true” estimates of reproducibility based on multiple measurements of the same quantity. Calculations based on the residuals will generally result in a conservative estimate, as it will also include systematic fluctuations in G_C with frequency. To avoid problems caused by measurements near the lowest usable frequency of a chamber, we will use data measured at frequencies greater than 1 GHz for estimation of the measurement reproducibility. The residuals appear to fall in a range of approximately -1 ± 3 dB. The actual measured average is -0.94 dB with a standard deviation of 1.7 dB.

Thus, the reproducibility of this measurement is approximately ± 3.4 dB.

The reproducibility is also indicative of how well G_C can be predicted using the two parameter model given in eq. 4. Using this model and the estimated values for a and b , we can predict the value of G_C within ± 3.4 dB.

For the data shown in figures 2 and 3, a spectrum analyzer was connected to the receiving antenna, and the measured received power was recorded. Spectrum analyzers can have large uncertainties in measurements of received power, so it is likely that instrumentation contributed significantly to the overall reproducibility of the measurement.

Figure 4. Chamber gain (a) and residuals (b) measured in chamber A using original measurement method.

We next present data from a different and much larger chamber which we will refer to as chamber A. In addition to being larger, chamber A had two large paddles placed in two opposite corners of the chamber, and these paddles extended from floor to ceiling. Figure 4a shows G_C for this chamber, measured with the same instrumentation and test procedure as before, with one significant exception: the spectrum analyzer connected to the receiving antenna was calibrated at

each frequency and resolution bandwidth with a standard power meter.

The data match the estimated curve fit very well, but there appears to be a significant bias between approximately 200 MHz and 1 GHz. Since the only difference between measurements made below and above 1 GHz is the antennas used for transmitting and receiving, we suspect this bias is caused by nonideal antenna effects, such as antenna mismatches and differences in antenna efficiency. All measurements of antenna mismatch indicate that the antennas used below 1 GHz are better matched than those used above 1 GHz, so if this were the only difference between the antennas, G_C should be greater below 1 GHz. This obviously is not the case, so we suspect that the efficiencies of the low frequency antennas are worse than those of the high frequency antennas. If the differences are due to differences in antenna efficiency, then it may be possible to use mode-stirred chambers to estimate the relative efficiency of antennas. This has not yet been verified, but is presented in the hopes of stimulating discussion and additional research.

The residuals of G_C are shown in Fig. 4b. The reproducibility of this measurement above 1 GHz is approximately ± 1.2 dB. We attribute the improvement in reproducibility to the improved calibration of the spectrum analyzer, although other factors may also play a role, as will be discussed later..

We repeated the evaluation of chamber A using the simplified test setup shown in Fig. 5. We used a VNA (vector network analyzer) in the hopes that the improved reliability and accuracy of such a system would result in better reproducibility. Another advantage of using a VNA for this measurement is the substantial increase in measurement speed. We were able to increase the number of measured frequencies by a factor of 50 and still reduce the measurement time by a factor of 2 or more.

Figure 5. VNA measurement system.

The chamber gain measured using the VNA system and the residuals of the chamber gain are presented in Fig. 6a and b, respectively. The bias between 200 MHz and 1 GHz is even more apparent here. The reproducibility of this measurement

Figure 6. Chamber gain (a) and residuals (b) of chamber A measured using VNA measurement system.

Figure 7. Chamber gain (a) and residuals (b) of NIST chamber with original paddle. Data measured using VNA measurement system.

Figure 8. Chamber gain (a) and residuals (b) of NIST chamber with original paddle. Data measured using VNA measurement system.

above 1 GHz is approximately ± 1 dB. From this it appears that using a network analyzer does result in data that are somewhat more reproducible than the original measurement system. These data also indicate that the measured values of G_C can be described using eq. (4) and the estimated values of a and b within ± 1 dB.

Finally, we used the VNA system to evaluate the NIST chamber. The chamber gain and residuals are presented in Fig. 7. We were surprised that the reproducibility was significantly worse in the NIST chamber (approximately ± 1.6 dB above 1 GHz) than the reproducibility measured in chamber A, since the same measurement system was used.

If the difference in reproducibility is not due to the measurement system, then the difference is most likely caused by some attribute of the chamber or paddle. We observed that the paddles in chamber A were large relative to the dimensions of the chamber, and hypothesized that this was the cause of the improved reproducibility. To test this theory, we extended the paddle in the NIST chamber from the original length of 1.8 m to 2.7 m, a length approximately equal to the width of the chamber. The resulting chamber gain and residuals are shown in Fig. 8. The reproducibility of the measurements in the NIST chamber improved to approximately ± 1 dB, which is similar to that measured in chamber A. The measured reproducibilities and the conditions under which they were measured are presented below in Table 1. In this table, we refer to the measurement system shown in Fig. 1 as the "original" measurement system, and the measurement system shown in Fig. 5 as the "VNA" measurement system. Also, we refer to the original paddle in the NIST chamber as the "small" paddle, and the modified paddle as the "large" paddle. The paddles in chamber A will simply be referred to as the "A" paddles.

Table 1. Measured reproducibility for various measurement methods, chambers, and paddle sizes.

Measurement Method	Chamber	Paddle	Reproducibility
Original	NIST	Small	± 3.4 dB
Original	A	A	± 1.2 dB
VNA	A	A	± 1.0 dB
VNA	NIST	Small	± 1.6 dB
VNA	NIST	Large	± 1.0 dB

The data presented in Table 1 suggest that the size of the paddle plays a significant role in measurement reproducibility. Previously, it was believed that the only requirement on the size of the paddle was that it needed to be electrically large, with a length greater than half of a wavelength ($\lambda/2$) at the lowest frequency of operation [1]. Our data show a significant improvement in chamber performance even at frequencies greater than 1 GHz, where the original paddle had a length of greater than 6

wavelengths. Even though the original paddle meets the length requirements stated above, the data suggest that a larger paddle improves reproducibility. We therefore think that the previous recommendation for the minimum size of a paddle is inadequate, and a new recommendation is required. We are now performing research to address this problem and hope to develop a new recommendation in the near future. It appears that any size criteria will be based on the dimensions of the chamber into which the paddle is to be placed.

CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that reproducibilities of approximately ± 1 dB are possible in a mode-stirred chamber, but that such reproducibilities require careful calibration, stable instrumentation, and mechanical stirrers or paddles that are substantially larger than was previously thought to be necessary. Our measurements suggest that the size of the paddle should be dictated more by the dimensions of the chamber than by the lowest frequency at which the chamber is to be operated.

Measurements made with a vector network analyzer were somewhat more reproducible than those made using separate signal sources and sensors. The increased speed and reliability of a VNA, combined with large paddles, resulted in data that shows biases, probably caused by nonideal antenna characteristics which were not previously observable due to the wide fluctuations in the measured data.

We have also shown that the average chamber gain can be described to within ± 1 dB using a simple two-parameter model. This should simplify the process of calibrating mode-stirred chambers, and also allow the characteristics of a chamber to be characterized by two parameters, a and b , rather than a graph of measured data.

These improvements and observations should result in measurements which are substantially more reliable than were previously possible.

REFERENCES

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